

Educational Process on a Traditional and Non-Traditional Basis

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Abstract: This article reveals the difference, shortcomings and achievements and content of traditional and non-traditional education, achieving quality and efficiency in the organization of the educational process in a traditional way or using non-traditional models.

Keywords: system, education, process, approach, difference, quality, efficiency, achievement, scarcity, formation.

The educational process is extremely complex. The effectiveness of education depends on the activity of teachers and students, the availability of teaching aids, the organizational, scientific, methodological perfection of the educational process, the need of society for knowledgeable people and other factors that have not yet been determined. Society requires high efficiency of education, based on its socio-political and economic needs.

Currently, when economic structures based on market relations are being created in Uzbekistan, the demand for people with broad, deep knowledge and the ability to apply knowledge in practice is increasing. A knowledgeable, enterprising, socially active person will find his place in the life of society and at work. In order for such activities to take place, it is necessary to form a knowledgeable and active personality, faithful to the idea of national independence.

It is necessary to organize all stages of education in such a way that it teaches young people to think comprehensively, giving them deep and well-founded knowledge. The requirement of our time is that the student's need for independent learning is formed during the educational process. The main essence of educational technology is to interest students and achieve complete assimilation of knowledge. The main goal of introducing pedagogical technology is the deep assimilation by the majority of students of the knowledge given in the learning process.

The most basic requirement in instructional technology-based learning is the provision of knowledge based on the knowledge and interests acquired by the learner through life experiences. Pedagogical technology requires not leaving room for the student's negative experience, even if the student's knowledge in the field of study is not enough, and recognizing that this is not the student's fault. If activity is shown, it is recommended to instill in students confidence in acquiring knowledge.

Pedagogical technology shows that recalling and activating students' knowledge in the field of learning is the basis for mastering new knowledge. Defining knowledge and preparation creates positive motivation for student activation and learning. When starting to study a topic, it can be animated in free conversation, discussion, brainstorming and other forms.

A traditional lesson is an educational model designed for a certain period of time; the educational process is more focused on the personality of the teacher and consists of the stages of introduction, clarification, consolidation and completion of the topic.

When the learning material is new and more complex, a traditional lesson is often the only method of learning.

It is known that the main purpose of a lesson in a traditional lesson is aimed at explaining more, with the teacher playing the role of the teacher and the students taking the role of the learner at the center of the educational process. It is determined on the basis of the opinions expressed by them during monitoring the degree of mastery of the subject being studied.

Thus, the purpose of the traditional lesson and its advantages are based on the following grounds:

- increasing the student's enthusiasm for learning;
- taking into account previously acquired knowledge;
- coordination of the speed of the educational process;
- support for student initiative and determination;
- learning through practice;
- providing two-way feedback;
- build the educational process correctly;
- teacher - a person who facilitates the learning process for students;
- assessment of the educational process.

The traditional teaching model uses more methods such as lecture, questions and answers, and practical exercises, so in these cases the effectiveness of a traditional lesson is much lower, and students become passive participants in the educational process. Research shows that while maintaining the traditional form of lessons, enriching it with modern teaching methods that activate student activity leads to an increase in student skill. To do this, the lesson process must be organized rationally, the teacher should increase the interest of students and constantly encourage their activity in the educational process, divide the educational material into small parts, reveal their content through discussion, debate, and intellectual attack. Requires small group work, exploration, use of role play techniques, presentation of various interesting examples, encouraging students to complete practical exercises independently, use of various assessment methods, use of teaching aids on site and in their own time.

Basic components of a traditional lesson:

1. Introduction:

- repetition of the material covered;
- explanation of the purpose of the lesson;
- familiarization with the content and lesson plan.

2. Coverage of a new topic:

- divide the new topic into small parts;
- maximum presentation of colorful examples;
- do not deviate from the topic;
- re-explanation of complex aspects of the material;
- checking the level of understanding of students;
- providing feedback;

3. Guided exercise:

- students perform the exercise (or task) independently, and the teacher controls and corrects them.

4. Independent exercise:

- students perform the exercise independently, without the help of a teacher.

5. Checking students' understanding

6. Conclusion.

A summary of the main concepts of the lesson topic and educational goals.

Advantages of the traditional learning model

- Helpful when learning specific educational concepts and sciences with specific skills.
- High level of control of the educational process and learning environment on the part of the teacher.
- Effective use of time.
- **Relies on precise scientific knowledge.**

Disadvantages of the traditional training model.

With the traditional teaching method, the educational goal is not clearly expressed in accordance with the requirements of the program; the teacher does not have a clear idea of the level and quality of the student's learning.

- students remain passive participants;
- full control of the teacher does not create motivation for all students;
- students cannot communicate directly with the teacher;
- since the level of memorization for all students is not the same, the level of assimilation for group lessons may be empty;
- **conditions for independent learning and decision-making have not been created.**

Non-traditional learning models

When using non-traditional learning models, students are primarily focused on independent thinking and independent learning. In this case, the teacher's activity consists not only of explaining the subject to students, but also of preparing assignments for them, monitoring the process of independent learning and assessing their final knowledge.

Non-traditional learning models can be divided into three:

- modeling;
- cooperative learning model;
- research **model of teaching.**

These teaching models are primarily student-centered, otherwise known as learner-centered teaching models.

Modeling is a method of creating a concise, simplified representation (model) of events and processes occurring in real life and in society in the classroom and in the classroom, involving personal participation of students and learning through activity.

The cooperative learning model is a method in which students learn by working in independent groups.

The inquiry model of learning is a method that allows students to conduct independent research aimed at solving a specific problem.

Benefits of a non-traditional learning model

- Bringing the content of training to good understanding.
- Ensuring timely communication.
- Creating conditions for the practical application of concepts.
- Offer various forms of training.
- High level of motivation.
- Good memorization of the studied material.
- Improving communication skills.
- Increased self-esteem.
- Positive attitude of students towards the content of the subject and the educational process.
- Contribute to the development of the student's ability to think independently.
- Not only help you master the content, but also develop critical and logical thinking.
- Formation of problem-solving skills.

Therefore, the advantages of the non-traditional teaching model are that a wide range of opportunities for students to actively participate in the lesson leads to better assimilation of the lesson content, while not only helping to master the content, but also promoting development. characterized by critical and logical, analytical thinking.

Disadvantages of the non-traditional learning model

- it takes a lot of time;
- lack of ability to always control students;
- the role of the teacher is low even when studying very complex material;
- since they are “weak” students, “strong” students also receive low grades;
- the requirement **for the teacher himself to have well-developed thinking abilities and problem-solving skills.**

It is worth noting that the effective use of non-traditional teaching methods depends, first of all, on the professional qualifications and skills of the teacher.

In conclusion, it should be said that the introduction of pedagogical technologies into the educational process is based on a systematic approach, especially in order to generalize and apply in life the work that needs to be done to create a modern pedagogical technological system of a systematic educational process. In the process of using the experience of pedagogical technologies of foreign countries, it is advisable to carry out the following activities:

1. Between the participants in the educational process - the teacher and the students: development of the curriculum, that is, when the teacher draws up a plan for studying a section and chapter, the activities of the student and teacher in this regard should find their expression. One of the principles of modern pedagogical technology-consistently planned distribution of educational work between teacher and student-requires the teacher to consistently manage the educational process.
2. Purposeful use of the possibilities of internal communication between science and interpersonal communication. Each major and minor learning module learned builds on what has been learned previously. It is also important to know interdisciplinary connections and the level of preparation of students. So, when introducing a student to the study of a new chapter, it is necessary to rely on existing knowledge; if the existing knowledge is not enough to study the new chapter, carry out intermediate preparation and only then move on to the next stage of learning, the study of knowledge.

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